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Marketization of Vocational Adult Education in Sweden

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Abstract

The focus of this paper is the organisation of vocational adult education on upper secondary level in Sweden, and specifically the process of marketization that has taken place here since the late 1990s. Swedish adult education on this level, including vocational as well as theoretical courses, is organised by the local municipality, but with national governing policies including a national curriculum. However, the courses and programmes *per se* are not necessarily organised by the municipality itself. There is a widespread system of procurement, which means that courses could also be organized by varying other providers, typically private training companies. That is, there are both private and public providers, but the training is paid for by the municipality, which also decides who will be admitted to different courses and has a responsibility for the quality assurance.

Keywords

marketization; adult education; vocational education and training; municipality

1 Introduction and background

The organisation of Swedish adult education has decisive differences in the ways market principles are applied, as compared to the development of compulsory and upper secondary school in Sweden, with a system of independent schools, which has been the main focus in prior research on marketization in the Swedish school system. There are a few studies that touch upon the topic of marketization of Swedish adult education and its consequences (e.g. Beach, 2004; Beach & Carlsson, 2004; Bjursell et al., 2015; Fejes, 2006; Fejes, Runesdotter & Wärvik, 2016; Lumsden Wass, 2004; Runesdotter, 2011), some of these with a focus on vocational adult education (Wärvik, 2013). The limited research on marketization of Swedish adult education is quite surprising bearing in mind that this quasi-market of adult education is large and encompass a high percentage of all students. In 2017, 45.9% of all students in municipal adult education (MAE) were enrolled in courses organised by a non-public provider, an increase from 14.4% in 1997. This can be compared to 25.2% of all students in upper secondary school being enrolled with an independent school in 2017 (Swedish National Agency of Education, 2019).

This paper is part of a research project that studies the marketization processes in Swedish adult education. Little is known about the present ways of organising vocational adult education in the Swedish municipalities, and our paper presents findings from the first step in the research project – a nationwide survey to the municipalities. In the project as a whole we are employing a policy ethnographic approach (cf. Ball, 2006; Beach, 1995; Gustafsson,

2003), an approach that also could be named trajectory study (e.g. Rizvi & Lingard, 2010). This approach is focusing the trajectory and transformation of policy, from the central context of influence to the local context of practice. In this first step we aim at providing an overview of how the national policy for the organisation of adult education is enacted on the local level, with a particular focus on vocational adult education.

The paper will answer the following research questions:

- How is vocational adult education organised in different municipalities in Sweden?
- How is educational counselling and quality assurance in vocational adult education organised in different municipalities?
- What character does the marketization of vocational adult education have in different municipalities?
- What differences are there between vocational and other adult education?

The analysis is based on data from a nationwide survey distributed to representatives for adult education in all Swedish municipalities (290), with 164 responses representing 201 municipalities (69%). (Some municipalities have a common organisation for MAE, and here one response represents more than one municipality.) The survey data is supplemented by background data from public statistics on the character of the municipalities, providing the basis for some comparisons between different types of municipality, mainly concerning size of population.

2 Results

2.1 The character of marketization of vocational adult education in municipalities

The survey results show that most municipalities in Sweden contract external providers for part of their MAE courses. Vocational education and training (VET), which is a part of MAE, have external providers to a somewhat higher degree than the general courses that mainly prepare for higher education. 29% of the responding municipalities organize most or all of the VET courses in MAE at their own municipal schools, while 34% mainly or only organize the general courses in MAE at their own schools. In the largest cities, 40–50% of MAE VET is organized by external providers.

These external providers are typically selected in a procurement process (in 77% of the municipalities). However, some of the larger municipalities have introduced a system called authorization. Procurement is in most cases organized with external providers submitting a description of courses they want to organize, based on criteria decided by the municipality, and the price for this. Thereafter, the municipality is choosing the provider with the lowest price that also fulfils the predefined criteria.

In the system of authorization, the municipality decides the price for each course/student, and defines criteria to be fulfilled for authorization as a legitimate provider of the course. When the municipality has authorized the providers, they have to recruit their students. The system of authorization means that the municipality does not have to spend time and resources on an extensive procurement process, but the result could also be that there are plenty of providers of the same course in one municipality. In some municipalities there are 30–40 providers that offer potential students a lot of courses and programmes. One municipality using this system has answered that they have 4,000 courses and 600 programmes (including apprenticeship VET programmes, but the figures include VET as well as general education).

2.2 Organising vocational adult education in different municipalities in Sweden

VET within MAE is rather extensive in Sweden. Most (76%) of the municipalities that responded to the survey have up to 300 students in VET for adults, but some larger municipalities have more than 1,500 VET students. However, there are still more students in general courses than in VET courses. Almost all municipalities (99% of those who responded) are also taking part in the national VAE initiative (vocational adult education, in Swedish *Yrkesvux*), a targeted initiative where municipalities can apply for and receive state subsidies for more study places in VET for adults. There has also been an option to use the subsidies for a combination of VET courses and courses in Swedish for immigrants, as a response to the high number of refugees that have arrived in Sweden last years. The condition for these state subsidies for VAE is that at least three municipalities have to build a partnership to cooperate in planning and organizing the courses. One of these municipalities are responsible for a common application, and reporting, for these VET courses, but the municipalities that cooperate share responsibility for fulfilling the requirements for subsidies.

It is relatively common that MAE is organized as distance courses. Among the responding municipalities, 66% say that VET is organized as distance courses to some extent, compared to 73% for general courses. Distance courses in VET to some or a high extent is more common in smaller than in larger municipalities, a pattern that we cannot see for general courses.

In larger municipalities, it is common that the same course is arranged by more than one provider. Many municipalities indicate that they – thanks to the fact that they have more providers – almost always can offer a study place for all applicants. Particularly, this is true for courses on compulsory school level (which actually is compulsory to provide for adults who lack this level of education), and for general courses on upper secondary level (which is not compulsory to provide). A number of municipalities have indicated that there are restrictions concerning study places in VET for adults.

In most municipalities (according to the survey results), adult students are free to choose between providers. If a (potential) student is not admitted at the school/provider they applied for, they normally have to apply again at the next opportunity, but it is also quite common that the person is offered a study place at another provider (in 24% of the municipalities) or in another municipality (30%). Many municipalities also buy single places in MAE VET in other municipalities, which are paid for via an inter-municipal agreement.

2.3 Educational counselling and quality assurance in vocational adult education

2.3.1 *Counselling*

Most municipalities have a common organization for educational counselling for all MAE (85% of responding municipalities). The counsellors are situated at the providers or centrally in the municipality. A number of municipalities have replied that they have a demand on the providers to offer educational and work counselling for their students, but it is formally the municipality that is responsible for educational and work counselling to be available.

In the open questions in the survey, we can see that the educational counsellors might have a central role in the admission process for MAE. The counsellors also have an important role as support for the students during the courses, by following up study results.

2.3.2 *Quality assurance*

The most common methods of quality assurance in the municipalities are student surveys (used in 84% of responding municipalities) and statistics concerning output (78%). In addi-

tion to this, quality assurance is conducted through report meetings (62%), written reports from providers (54%), site visits at the providers (49%), and surveys to providers (42%). More than half of the respondents do not make site visits at the providers for quality assurance. In addition to these ways of quality assurance, answers to open questions show that there is also quality assurance through statistics of grades and follow-up of employment rates after studying in adult education.

Most municipalities that have answered the survey (68%) have not taken any specific measures based on the quality assurance work. However, measures to secure quality, and sanctions for providers as a result of lacking quality, are more common in the large city areas than in small municipalities. Measures taken due to lacking quality are for example to set up an action plan, a fine order, discontinued admission, or that the contract is cancelled.

3 Discussion

The findings from the survey show that the marketization leads to a flexibility for adult education with a freedom of choice for the students regarding study pace and form, while there are good opportunities for adults to be admitted to VET as well as general courses in MAE. However, the marketization causes problems for the municipalities who have difficulties fulfilling the demand for flexibility. Large organizations and appeals to procurements, short-term contracts that make it difficult to plan, as well as the risk of over-establishment are other problems described in the wake of the marketization. There are also answers that suggest resource shortages in MAE. In some municipalities, adult education is described as 'invisible' in relation to upper secondary education, others describe problems with recruiting qualified teachers for MAE and some that there are no resources for students in need of special support.

The national VAE initiative has led to cooperation between municipalities regarding MAE and has increased the opportunities of adults for admission to VET. However, the short time frame of subsidies received for VAE makes it difficult for the municipalities to plan and arrange MAE VET. There is also a requirement for co-financing from the municipalities to receive the subsidies. The model used for this is described as very costly for smaller municipalities and therefore limits the study places in VAE.

Educational counselling and quality assurance are key elements in MAE. In the marketized flexible adult education with a wide variety of education programmes and several providers who offer the same courses, some at distance, some at semi-distance, some in school, the counsellor is described as having an important role in guiding (potential) students in choosing providers, programmes and courses (when, how, where). The counsellor also follows up on the students' learning outcomes, helps them with course changes, problems etc. In cases with restrictions concerning study places in MAE VET the study counsellor can also have a role to act as a gate-keeper in the selection process.

The large number of providers in MAE also place high demands on quality assurance. The survey shows that the quality is largely 'student cantered' with a focus on student surveys and statistics concerning output. However, it is not so common to make site visits at the providers for quality assurance. In some of the survey answers, shortages both in the quality of education and quality assurance by external educational providers are described. Some of the open answers of the survey also describe problems with cheating when it comes to the grading of courses. 'We often see that students coming from other municipalities with grades from procured private providers receive grades in courses they should not have. It's cheated. [...] Every time that happens we break a bit. I have lots of similar examples. It is really, really hard then to keep the banner high.'

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